

Abstract submitted to the Marine Energy Research Conference

Title: The St. Anthony Falls Laboratory, University of Minnesota: 86 years of hydraulic modeling and simulation research.

Type: Poster

Abstract (500 Words):

The University of Minnesota St. Anthony Falls Laboratory is one of our nation's core hydraulic research facilities. Located in Minneapolis, Minnesota within the Mississippi River, the history around the creation of this facility and the evolution of the Lab over the last 86 years is a fascinating journey. Today, SAFL is a thriving research center with impactful research in engineering hydraulics, renewable energy, stormwater engineering, and ecohydraulics; utilizing many of the original large-scale hydraulic facilities and infrastructure. In this poster, we will showcase the history of this university-based research laboratory. Additionally, we will summarize key energy research in marine hydrokinetic energy, off-shore wind energy, river restoration, and hydropower. SAFL is also a member of the Testing Expertise and Access for Marine Energy Research (TEAMER™) program, which is sponsored by the U.S. Department of Energy and directed by the Pacific Ocean Energy Trust. The poster will provide a summary of CFD and physical modeling capabilities accessible through the TEAMER program.